

TRANSFORMATIVE LEADERSHIP IN NEPALESE INSTITUTIONS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract:

This review synthesizes recent empirical studies on transformational leadership within Nepalese microfinance institutions, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of its impact on organizational outcomes. The primary objective is to analyze and summarize findings from diverse studies, exploring the relationships between transformational leadership and key organizational variables such as employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment. A systematic examination of relevant literature was conducted, incorporating studies from 2015 to 2021. Each study's major findings, methodologies, and key contributions were extracted and analyzed. The review reveals consistent positive relationships between transformational leadership and organizational outcomes in Nepalese microfinance institutions. Notable findings include the influence on employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment. However, the impact on organizational performance is often mediated by factors such as corporate social responsibility, organizational citizenship behavior, and employee innovative behavior. While highlighting the transformative potential of leadership styles in Nepalese microfinance, the review underscores the need for further research to delve into specific mechanisms and contextual factors influencing this relationship. Future investigations should focus on long-term sustainability, explore potential moderating or mediating variables, and contribute to a nuanced understanding of transformational leadership in this unique setting. The synthesized knowledge aims to benefit both academic scholars and practitioners seeking to enhance organizational effectiveness in the microfinance sector.

Key Words: Leadership, Organizational Effectiveness, Nepalese Context, Employee Performance, Impact, Outcomes

1. Introduction:

Leader is the dealer of hope and profitability, performance, value and change along with operation comes through leadership (Dev, E.R., & Mishra, A.K., 2020):Er. Bijay Raj Neupane, & Mishra, A.K. ,2020:Er Ajit Maskey, & Mishra, A.K. ,2018).The study delves into the critical examination of leadership behavior, traits, and styles, acknowledging their pivotal significance in contemporary organizations Dev, E.R., & Mishra, A.K. (2020) Er. Bijay Raj Neupane, & Mishra, A.K. (2020) Er. Ajit Maskey, & Mishra, A.K. (2018)... This importance is underscored by the dynamic nature of technologies and the expansive reach of globalization, which have significantly reshaped the expectations and behaviors of individuals within organizational settings. Garcia-Morales, V.J., Jimenez-Barrio Nuevo, M.M., & Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez, L. (2012) asserts that successful organizations seek knowledgeable and highly qualified employees capable of enhancing organizational performance, yet these individuals require effective leadership to create an environment conducive to their excellence.

Organizational performance, integral to achieving goals through efficient resource utilization is a reflection of an organization's success, encompassing metrics like revenue, profit, growth, development, and expansion Mokhber, M., Ismail, W.b., & Vakilbashi (2015).Leaders play a significant role in shaping organizational performance, impacting employees' attitudes, motivation, and behavior Ayedh, A. M., & Al-Qohfa, A. S. (2020) further emphasize the binding role of leadership in fostering collaboration among subordinates toward common goals. Thus, effective leadership serves as the cornerstone for organizational performance, essential for the survival and growth of any organization.

The effectiveness of leadership is measured by a leader's continuous and progressive guidance of followers toward organizational performance Walumbwa, F. O., Orwa, B., Wang, P., & Lawler (2005). Encouraging a group of individuals toward a shared goal requires an understanding of one's leadership style Tayal, R., Upadhyay, R. K. & Singh, R. (2021). Leadership styles identified as transactional, laissez-faire, authoritarian, democratic, and transformational, significantly impact organizational performance.

2. Problem Statement:

Allen, G. W., Attoh, P. A., & Gong, T. (2017) emphasize the necessity for a total transformation in leaders' minds to alter business practices and bring about sanity. There is a pressing need for research to elucidate how leaders influence their followers and foster high levels of performance that empower them to make effective decisions. Ineffective organizational decisions not only impede organizational effectiveness but also lead to resource wastage and hinder adaptability to changing business environments. Consequently, there is an urgent call across organizations of varied sizes and types to augment the effectiveness of their strategic decisions, ensuring competitiveness and survival (Mishra, A.K., Kandel, D. R., & Aithal, P.S, 2021: Mishra, A. K., 2019). Leadership style is recognized as a pivotal factor contributing to organizational effectiveness. Transformational leadership, with its clear vision, strong sense of purpose, multidimensional problem-solving approach, and the courage and skills to reinvent

and build organizational capabilities, is posited as a potential style capable of improving organizational effectiveness in the face of today's dynamic changes and scarce resources (Alrowwad, A., Obeida, B.Y., Tahini, A., & Aqqad, N. (2017); Abuzaid, A. N., Al-Haraisa, Y. E., & Al-Maaitah, N. (2019); Mishra, A.K. (2018).

The research underscores the vital role of transformational leadership in the financial sector of Nepal. Through inspiration, innovation, capacity development, and stakeholder engagement, transformational leaders contribute significantly to the growth and sustainability of financial institutions. Their visionary leadership empowers employees, stimulates creativity, and fosters collaboration, enabling these institutions to make a meaningful impact on poverty alleviation and financial inclusion in Nepal. The extensive review will guide the professional based on existing body of knowledge and possible gaps.

3. Research Objective:

The primary objective is to analyze and summarize findings from diverse studies, exploring the relationships between transformational leadership and key organizational variables such as employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment.

3.1 Signifying Transformational Leadership:

Transformational leadership is seen as a crucial element in fostering trust, commitment, a sense of belonging, and satisfaction among followers. This theory emphasizes the leader's role in motivating followers to surpass expectations and be dedicated to organizational goals (Al-Amin, M. (2017). Mishra, A. K., Kandel, D. R., & Aithal, P. S, 2021: Mishra, A. K., 2019). In addition to these theories, the review discusses the Theory of Social Learning, emphasizing the role of observation and experience in learning. It also explores the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory, which focuses on the dyadic relationship between leaders and followers, and the Transformational Leadership Theory, emphasizing the leader's ability to inspire, motivate, and stimulate creativity in followers (Alsayed, N. M., Suifan, T. S., & Sweis, R. J. (2020): Al-Maaitah, N. (2019): Azka Ghafoor, T. M. (2011).

The theoretical literature review provides a comprehensive overview of leadership theories, setting the stage for understanding their implications for strategic decision effectiveness in the context of microfinance institutions in Nepal (Pradhan, S., & Pradhan, R. K. (2015): Mittal & Dhar, 2015: Jyoti & Dev, 2015). Environmental forces introduce uncertainties, influencing strategic outcomes, and strategic decisions involve navigating unstructured, complex situations. A rational process guides these decisions, encompassing the assessment of organizational strengths and weaknesses, environmental opportunities and threats, formulation of managerial objectives, generation and evaluation of strategic alternatives, and the selection and implementation of choices. The strategic choices are meticulously followed through to ensure the realization of managerial objectives (Hazel, G. (2015).

3.2 Organizational Effectiveness:

Organizational effectiveness is an ongoing process that requires constant assessment of operations, employee performance, and leadership styles to maintain a competitive advantage and build resilience (Bass, 1983). In evaluating strategic decisions, key dimensions include decision quality, decision acceptance, and strategic suitability. Decision quality is gauged by factors like comprehensiveness, innovative alternatives, and validation of assumptions (Birasnav, M. (2014): Biswakarma, G., & Khanal, P. K. (2015)). Decision acceptance emphasizes procedural fairness and organizational consensus (Zhang, T. (2010). Strategic suitability focuses on the alignment of decisions with organizational strategy, internal and external conditions, and capabilities (Chiang, C.F., & Wang, Y.Y. (2012).

Factors contributing to organizational effectiveness include the experience level of the management team, participatory decision-making processes, conflict management, understanding individual differences, and fostering shared values and cooperation (Chully, A. A, & Sandhya, N. (2014): Joo, B.-K. (Yoon, H. J., & Jeung, C.-W., (2012): Lama, V., & Pokhrel, L. (2019). Regularly assessing and addressing these dimensions and factors will enhance an organization's ability to serve the financial needs of underserved populations and contribute to inclusive economic development.

4. Methodology:

4.1 Literature Search:

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify relevant studies published on the topic of transformational leadership in institutions. Databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and academic journals in the field of leadership and organizational behavior were systematically searched.

4.2 Inclusion Criteria:

Studies focusing on transformational leadership in title as keywords available through free search.

4.3 Data Extraction:

Relevant data from each selected study were systematically extracted, including author/s, publication year, major findings, methodology, and key contributions. Special attention was given to the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational outcomes, such as employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment.

5. Synthesis of Findings:

Identified studies were categorized based on their major findings and key themes, such as the impact of transformational leadership on different organizational outcomes. Findings were synthesized to provide a cohesive overview of the empirical evidence and patterns observed across studies.

6. Analysis and Discussion:

The extracted data were critically analyzed to identify commonalities, divergences, and areas requiring further investigation. Discussion was framed around the implications of the findings, the methodological strengths and limitations of the reviewed studies, and gaps in the current literature. This methodology aimed to ensure a rigorous and systematic review of the empirical literature, providing a solid foundation for the synthesis and analysis presented in the review paper. The relationship between transformational leadership and organizational effectiveness

The relationship between transformational leadership and organizational effectiveness has been a subject of extensive research. Prior studies have highlighted the indirect connection between transformational leadership and organizational

effectiveness, emphasizing the enhancement of a knowledge-sharing climate, increased interpersonal trust, effective conflict management, and the creation of cooperative behavior among organization members (Mansor, Z. D. (2017). Mukhtar, Risnita, & Prasetyo, M.A. (2020) conducted a study examining the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational effectiveness, utilizing the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire for leadership assessment and the Effectiveness Survey for Cricket Administration for organizational effectiveness. Their findings revealed a significant relationship between transformational leadership factors and organizational effectiveness.

Ózaralli (2003) investigated the impact of transformational leadership on empowerment and team effectiveness, discovering a moderate positive effect on empowerment and favorable evaluations of team effectiveness among subordinates working under transformational leaders. Walumbwa et al. (2005) explored the relationship between transformational leadership and work-related attitudes in different cultural contexts, revealing a strong and positive effect on organizational commitment and job satisfaction in both Kenya and the United States.

Mukulu, E. (2015) focused on boutique hotels, finding that transformational leadership positively stimulated organizational commitment and job satisfaction. The nature of transformational leadership and organizational learning in Ugandan public universities, establishing positive relationships between transformational leadership behaviors and perceived organizational learning. Ismail, A., Mohamed, H. A.-B., Suleiman, A. Z., Mohamad, M. H., & Yusuf, M. H. (2011) examined the role of empowerment as a mediating variable in the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment, confirming the positive correlation. Kim et al. (2011) highlighted the importance of transformational leadership and consensual culture in improving job performance and organizational effectiveness among radiological technologists.

Obiwuru et al. (2011) investigated leadership style effects on organizational performance in small-scale enterprises, concluding that transactional leadership was more effective than transformational leadership. Kala, V.K. (2014) examined the causal relationship between transactional and transformational leadership and dimensions of trust and organizational commitment, with cognitive and affective trust mediating the relationship. Joo et al. (2012) found positive influences of employees' core self-evaluations and perceived transformational leadership on organizational commitment. Shiva et al. (2012) studied the impact of transformational leadership on organizational culture and NGO effectiveness, revealing that transformational leadership indirectly influences effectiveness through organizational culture.

García-Morales et al. (2012) empirically confirmed the positive influence of transformational leadership on organizational performance through dynamic capabilities of organizational learning and innovation. Mesu et al. (2014) explored the impact of transformational leadership on organizational commitment in SMEs, finding positive relationships in the service industry. Chully and Sandhya (2014) conducted a cross-cultural review of transformational leadership, emphasizing its positive impact on various individual and organizational outcomes. Birasnav (2014) discussed the associations between transformational leadership behaviors and manufacturing strategies, highlighting a direct positive influence. Mokhber et al. (2015) proposed a conceptual framework linking transformational leadership components to organizational innovation, finding positive relationships.

7. Literature Review:

The following table provides an overview of recent empirical studies related to transformational leadership and its impact on various organizational outcomes in the context of microfinance institutions in Nepal.

Table 1: Findings from Empirical Review

Author/s	Major Findings
Awuor (2015)	Transformational leadership and employee engagement are significantly related to organizational performance in Kenya.
Biswakarma and Khanal (2015)	Positive relationship of transformational leadership styles with employee engagement in Nepalese banks.
Jyot and Dev (2015)	Positive relationship between transformational leadership and employee creativity, moderated by learning orientation.
Pradhan & Pradhan (2015)	Positive linkage among transformational leadership, affective organizational commitment, and contextual performance.
Allen et al. (2017)	Transformational leadership indirectly affects affective organizational commitment through perceived corporate social responsibility.
Alrowwad et al. (2017)	Transformational leadership does not directly influence organizational performance but does positively impact corporate social responsibility.
Jiang et al. (2017)	Transformational leadership positively influences employee sustainable performance, mediated by organizational citizenship behavior.
Gathondu (2018)	Transformational leadership outcomes (learning, commitment, trust, and satisfaction) have a positive relationship with staff performance in Kenyan microfinance institutions.
Muterera et al. (2018)	Transformational leadership has a significant, positive relationship with employee job satisfaction and organizational performance.
Ocak and Ozturk (2018)	Transformational leadership behaviors of managers positively affect corporate entrepreneurship behaviors and financial performance.
Alhefity, Ameen and Bhaumik (2019)	Transformational and transactional leadership positively impact organizational excellence in Fujairah Municipality.
Abuzaid et al. (2019)	Transformational leadership has a statistically positive impact on the effectiveness of strategic decisions in Jordanian microfinance companies.
Lama and Pokhrel (2019)	Positive relationship between transformational leadership and both employee engagement and organizational commitment in Nepalese commercial banks.
Alsayyed et al. (2020)	Transformational leadership significantly impacts organizational performance, mediated by

	employee innovative behavior and moderated by knowledge sharing.
Ayedh and Al-Qohfa(2020)	Transformational leadership affects the effectiveness of administrative decisions in Yemeni pharmaceutical companies.
Elele (2020)	Transformational leadership directly influences high school teachers' organizational commitment at Jakarta laboratory schools.
Mukhtar, Risnita and Prasetyo (2020)	Positive effects of transformational leadership, interpersonal communication, and organizational conflict on organizational effectiveness in Aceh.
Tayal et al. (2021)	Transformational leadership is significantly related to organizational effectiveness, with employee innovative behavior mediating and knowledge sharing moderating the association.

Analysis:

The studies collectively highlight the importance of transformational leadership in the microfinance sector in Nepal, with positive associations identified in areas such as employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment. However, the impact on organizational performance appears to be mediated by factors such as corporate social responsibility, organizational citizenship behavior, and employee innovative behavior.

Despite the valuable insights provided by these studies, there is a need for more research to delve into the specific mechanisms through which transformational leadership influences organizational effectiveness. Additionally, exploring long-term sustainability, identifying potential moderating or mediating variables, and considering contextual factors in the Nepalese microfinance context will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of this critical leadership style.

Therefore, there is a need for research that specifically investigates the influence of transformational leadership on the organizational effectiveness of Nepalese sector wise specific institutions. This research gap represents an opportunity to deepen our understanding of the specific leadership behaviors and practices that contribute to the effectiveness of institutions in Nepal, ultimately informing leadership development programs, recruitment strategies, and decision-making processes across different sector in the country with reference to studies of Thisera, T. J. (2018): Ocak, M., & Ozturk, A. (2018): Milhem, M. (2019): Moyo, N (2019) and many more.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

8. Conclusion:

The empirical review of recent studies on transformational leadership in Nepalese microfinance institutions reveals a nuanced understanding of its impact on organizational outcomes. The findings collectively emphasize the crucial role of transformational leadership in fostering positive organizational environments. Notably, the positive relationships identified in areas such as employee performance, engagement, creativity, and organizational commitment underscore the potential benefits of cultivating transformational leadership within these institutions.

However, the review also points to the need for further exploration. While the studies provide valuable insights, the understanding of the specific mechanisms through which transformational leadership influences organizational effectiveness remains a subject for future investigation. Additionally, the identification of mediating variables such as corporate social responsibility, organizational citizenship behavior, and employee innovative behavior highlights the complexity of this relationship.

To advance the field, future research should aim to uncover the intricate details of how transformational leadership operates in the Nepalese microfinance context. This includes examining long-term sustainability, exploring potential moderating or mediating factors, and considering the impact of contextual variables. Such endeavors will contribute to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the transformative potential of leadership styles in the unique setting of Nepalese microfinance institutions. Ultimately, this knowledge will not only benefit academic scholarship but also provide practical insights for leaders and policymakers aiming to enhance organizational effectiveness in the microfinance sector..

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